

Extracting metadata from grey literature using small fine-tuned language models

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Abstract

The increasing volume of grey literature, such as reports, theses, presentations and blog posts produced by public sector organisations and academia, poses significant cataloguing, discoverability, and accessibility challenges in digital libraries. To help address these challenges, the National Library of Finland has been developing tools and methods for extracting metadata from grey literature publications. We have compiled a data set of Finnish grey literature that can be used for training and evaluation. Our current main approach is the use of fine-tuned small language models that can be hosted on local computing infrastructure. We have also extended the Meteor metadata extraction tool with support for LLM-based extraction. Our evaluations show that metadata extraction using our methods can achieve F1 scores of 90%–92% averaged across 13 different metadata fields. The system is ready for demonstrations, but significant work remains before it can be put into production use.

Keywords

metadata extraction, large language models, grey literature

1. Introduction

Grey literature is usually defined as material and research that is not being published through established commercial or academic channels. It can include reports, presentations, blog posts, briefs, theses etc. Grey literature is nowadays mainly published as PDF files on institutional web sites as well as institutional repositories. The publications themselves as well as metadata practices for grey literature are very heterogeneous, complicating their cataloguing and preservation and reducing their findability in discovery systems.

The National Library of Finland handles many forms of grey literature within its systems and workflows. We currently operate 14 institutional repositories for various organisations including Finnish academic libraries and public institutions. Grey literature is also among the materials deposited to us via the legal deposit system.

To improve the metadata workflows for grey literature, we have been developing tools and systems for extracting metadata directly from PDF publications. Metadata extraction has traditionally been performed using systems such as GROBID [1] and CERMINE [2], which combine rules and simple machine learning models. Recent developments in the field of machine learning and artificial intelligence have significantly improved the quality of extraction [3, 4].

Our system comprises a curated data set of grey literature publications, a set of fine-tuned small language models for metadata extraction, an evaluation framework as well as a metadata extraction application. The system is ready for demonstrations, but more work remains before it can be deployed into production settings and workflows. We have been collaborating on this task with the National Library of Norway and given presentation about it at the SWIB24 conference¹.

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¹<https://forum.swib.org/t/automating-metadata-extraction-and-cataloguing-experiences-from-the-national-libraries-of-norway-and-finland/>

2. FinGreyLit data set

In order to systematically build and evaluate solutions for metadata extraction, we have collected a curated data set of Finnish grey literature called FinGreyLit. It consists of information about approximately 1,600 born-digital PDF documents that can be found on the web and contains basic Dublin Core style metadata about each document. The core data set was originally collected from many Finnish institutional repositories, but it has since been extended with documents that have been obtained by legal deposit by the National Library of Finland.

The FinGreyLit data set is split into 75% train and 25% test subsets. Its documents are also categorised by document type, by source repository and by language (mainly Finnish, Swedish and English, with a small number of documents in Northern Sámi). The data set, along with code for the experiments and evaluations described in this paper, is available on GitHub².

3. Metadata extraction using small language models

To perform metadata extraction, we have experimented with pretrained open-weight small language models of up to 24B parameters, mostly concentrating on the 4B to 12B range due to ease of deployment.

A purely prompting-based approach using the DSPy framework [5] did not give very good results. Instead of pure prompting, we have used the Axolotl toolkit [6] to fine-tune many different small language models using the FinGreyLit train subset as training data. In the training process, we use text extracted using the PyMuPDF4LLM³ library from the first six and last two pages of the PDF document as the input and the curated metadata in JSON format as the target output. The fine-tuning was performed in the University of Helsinki HPC environment on a single Nvidia A100 GPU with 80GB VRAM.

Currently, our main model is based on Gemma 3 4B [7], which performs well for its size and is suitable for running on local computing infrastructure, avoiding the need for cloud-based AI systems that suffer from privacy and copyright issues. Our fine-tuned Gemma model is available on HuggingFace Hub⁴.

4. Meteor tool

While working on metadata extraction, we have collaborated with the National Library of Norway, which is facing similar challenges in their process to catalogue and preserve PDF reports published by Norwegian public sector organisations. To assist their cataloguers in this task, they have developed an open source metadata extraction tool called Meteor⁵. It is based on a more traditional rule-based approach utilising regular expressions, keywords and heuristics. Meteor is implemented in Python code and is already being used in their production workflows. The tool is structured as a microservice, with a lightweight REST API for integrating it as a backend for cataloguing systems and a simple administration user interface for testing it on individual documents.

Originally, Meteor did not perform well on the FinGreyLit test set, mainly because our documents are more diverse than the Norwegian reports it was developed for. Thus, we have extended it with a module that uses an external LLM service (llama.cpp [8] on an Nvidia V100 GPU with 16GB VRAM) for processing PDF document text with our fine-tuned LLM instead of relying on built-in rules. We also extended the Meteor user interface to allow selecting the extraction method (*LLMExtractor* for the external LLM configured in settings or *Finder* for the original Meteor rules); the form is shown in figure 1 and the extraction result in figure 2. The results can be inspected and verified manually by the user.

At the workshop, we will demonstrate metadata extraction using both the original Meteor rules and the external LLM on different kinds of grey literature documents and discuss our findings. Currently, the demonstration application is available for testing only by contacting the authors.

²<https://github.com/NatLibFi/FinGreyLit>

³<https://pymupdf.readthedocs.io/en/latest/pymupdf4llm/>

⁴<https://huggingface.co/NatLibFi/gemma-3-4b-it-GreyLitLM-GGUF>

⁵<https://github.com/NationalLibraryOfNorway/meteor>

METEOR

[API-dokumentasjon](#)

[Swagger API-dokumentasjon](#)

Figure 1: Meteor administration user interface form for testing metadata extraction, extended to support metadata extraction either using internal rules (Finder) or an external language model (LLMExtractor).

Filename: https://www.doria.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/189909/wang_qingbo.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y

Field	Value	Origin	Registry
year	2024	{'type': 'LLM'}	
language	eng	{'type': 'LLM'}	
title	Wood-Derived Functional Biomaterials towards 3D Bioprinting	{'type': 'LLM'}	
publisher	Åbo Akademi University	{'type': 'LLM'}	
publicationType			
author	Firstname: Qingbo Lastname: Wang	{'type': 'LLM'}	
isbn	9789521244032	{'type': 'LLM'}	
issn			

Figure 2: Meteor testing user interface showing LLM-based metadata extraction results for a doctoral thesis.

5. Evaluation

We have evaluated the original Meteor approach as well as three different fine-tuned language models. The results are summarised in table 1. We use average F1 scores as the metric, combining precision and recall when compared to the curated gold standard test set. We calculated the average scores separately for the seven fields supported by Meteor and all 13 fields extracted using the language models.

For comparison, we also include a simple baseline that predicts nothing. This is an effective strategy for some metadata elements such as DOI, alternate title or printed ISBN, which occur very rarely in the documents and thus an empty prediction is often correct.

The baseline method got an average F1 score of 42% (26% for the seven fields). The original Meteor heuristics achieved a F1 score of 65% across the seven metadata field it supports. The language models achieved scores between 86%–87% and 92%, with the largest model, Mistral NeMo 12B⁶, receiving the highest score. Gemma 3 with its 4B parameters received a score of 90%. The smallest model, Qwen2.5 0.5B [9], is mainly suitable for CPU-only inference on a developer laptop.

⁶<https://mistral.ai/news/mistral-nemo>

Table 1

Per-field evaluation results (average F1 scores) for different metadata extraction methods. We have calculated the averages separately for the seven fields supported by Meteor and all 13 fields extracted by language models.

	baseline	Meteor	Qwen2.5 0.5B	Gemma3 4B	Mistral NeMo 12B
language	0%	97%	99%	99%	100%
title	0%	40%	74%	87%	92%
alt_title	76%	-	83%	87%	87%
creator	17%	65%	79%	87%	89%
publisher	8%	8%	76%	80%	86%
year	14%	72%	89%	91%	93%
e-isbn	63%	83%	89%	92%	90%
e-issn	78%	86%	92%	92%	94%
p-isbn	72%	-	92%	92%	92%
p-issn	83%	-	96%	96%	96%
doi	91%	-	99%	100%	100%
type_coar	0%	-	80%	82%	89%
average (7 fields)	26%	65%	86%	90%	92%
average (13 fields)	42%	-	87%	90%	92%

6. Discussion and future work

A benefit of language models is that they have built-in knowledge of conventions such as different ways of expressing author names and roles. In the fine-tuning process, they can be guided to transform e.g. titles and person names into the expected format for cataloguing in terms of letter case, punctuation and use of abbreviations instead of literally transcribing what is in the document.

Our current main challenges include a) reliable extraction of text from heterogeneous PDF files, b) capturing information that is only represented as images, c) built-in limitations of the Meteor tool (e.g., only a few metadata elements are supported), and d) the constant evolution of language models and their surrounding ecosystem of tools and practices.

Future work includes further testing of the tools in real world use cases and starting to draft a potential service around it, likely replacing the Meteor tool with a custom software implementation. We expect to further refine the model fine-tuning methods in order to improve output quality. Recently, Vision Language Models (VLMs) have improved a lot and we plan to test a VLM-based approach instead of relying purely on the text layer of PDF files. VLMs could also enable the use of digitised publications and smartphone photographs of printed books (e.g. title pages) as starting points for metadata extraction.

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Declaration on Generative AI

The authors have not employed any Generative AI tools for preparing this paper.

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